

APPLICATIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) IN LIBRARIES

Pawar Shubhangi Raosaheb

Research Student

Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada
University, Sambhajinagar

E-mail: shubhavi1527@gmail.com

Mo.No.7350772087/7588664341

Dr. Nilima R. Bankar

Research Guide

Librarian (Associate Professor)
Shri Muktanand College, Gangapur.
Aurangabad.

E-Mail: nilima.r.bankar@gmail.com

Mo. No. 9850224373/8208212152

ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) has brought about new prospects for expanding research in all areas. The presence of artificial intelligence technologies in all spheres of work has made the future promising. The Application of AI has contributed immensely to the provision and use of library information resources and has helped to achieve the goals and objectives of the library. Librarians need to be innovative in their thinking to stay relevant in their jobs because AI has found numerous applications in libraries ranging from book filing to book delivery. Its application brought about several new possibilities in the library such as connecting physical library information resources and electronic resources, and also Associating video help with physical information materials and objects. The chapter discussed some components of AI, library services it can be applied to, the benefits of its application, as well as the challenges libraries face in the application of artificial intelligence in the library.

Key Word:- Artificial Intelligence, Libraries

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) is an aspect of computational science that is concerned with making machines provide answers to complicated and difficult issues in a way that humans do. Human cognitive characteristics are appropriated, modeled, and integrated as algorithms in a manner that computers understand and can process to give an output or result. In its logical approach, Artificial Intelligence is a neural network, which is a network of artificial neurons or nodes that mimics the human biological processes of neurons. It was developed in a system to imitate the structural organization of the neural activities of humans. The neural network collectively generates informed decisions as they pass from one to the other. It models biological

processes and makes best guesses as they process data. Neural networks are hence a certain form of machine learning system, which is an AI system. Artificial intelligence started as a field in the 1950s and its application to libraries started in the 1990s.

COMPONENTS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

The two major components of artificial intelligence are machine learning and its subset, deep learning. Ali, et al, (2020) among other scholars identified the following components of artificial intelligence.

Machine Learning

Machine Learning (ML) is an artificial intelligence (AI) technology that enables developed systems to train and gain new knowledge on their own without being specifically taught. Data is fed into a consuming machine-learning system, which controls how the system outputs or reacts. The programming can also be unique; a system for machine learning can be trained to recognize certain models in case studies by exposure to the enormous data collection of the case study. The system may also be created repeatedly when its own output is used as an input or data source, it can be tested and programmed on an ongoing basis. ML systems can even be constructed assets or groups where there is a pair, each in collaboration or in competition, of machine learning systems. (ALA 2019). The focus is on developing computer algorithms that access and use data for training themselves. Machine learning systems can play a pivot function in the provision of library information resources and services. Examples of Machine Learning tools within AI include: Big Data, Text Data Mining (TDM), Robotics, Pattern Recognition, and Chatbots.

Deep Learning

Deep Learning (DL) is a subset of machine learning. The human brain inspires the algorithms and artificial neural networks which then learn from enormous amounts of data. Even with a data set that is unstructured turned, very diversified and interconnected, machines solve complicated issues through deep learning. Natural Language Processing (NLP), Image Processing (IM), and Neural Networking are examples of AI tools used in the context of Deep Learning.

Natural Language Processing

Natural Language Processing (NLP) allows computers to understand the primary language impressions within a question or solution. The design of subject indexing, development of information retrieval systems, and bibliometrics are all examples of how NLP can be used as crucial components in the establishment of a digital library. Researchers noted that text mining techniques are used in efforts to organize vast amounts of language data (i.e., converting unstructured data to structured data) and to define concepts conveyed in textual form (e.g., sentiment and emotion analysis in speeches and comments).

Pattern Recognition

Pattern recognition automatically recognizes patterns and consistencies in data sets. Pattern recognition is an example of machine learning, as well as other AI technologies such as data mining and knowledge discovery in databases. Pattern recognition is centered on a priori knowledge or statistical information collected from the structures. Patterns to be classified are frequently clusters of observations or measurements that define points in a suitable multi-dimensional space. The usage of the Completely Automated Public Turing Test (CAPTCHA) to check if the user is a robot or a human at the front end interface is an example.

Robotics

Library activities involve plenty of manual work, which can be partially or fully done effectively with the help of robots. Technology has advanced libraries in many ways; Robots are being used instead of humans in various library operations, especially those tasks which are hazardous and time-consuming. A robot is a mechanized device that uses artificial intelligence methods to complete automated activities under direct human guidance, pre-defined instructions, or a set of generic procedures. Robot such as that in the PESIST central library in India, helps with filing, sorting, and replacing books on the shelf. Libraries with a huge collection now use robots for inventory purposes. The 'Robbie' robot developed by the Temasek Polytechnic Library can scan more than 32000 books per day. Another robot from the same library named 'Bobbie', is able to deliver materials like newspapers, magazines, brochures, and can welcome as well as direct guests and students to various locations. Robots are now being programmed to answer Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs) that library patrons may have. Even though robots have

artificial intelligence, they cannot be as intelligent as humans as they are man-made and need a human touch to get operated.

Chatbots

Chatbots (referred to as intelligent agents, digital assistants, or virtual agents) are software applications which can converse intelligently, whether by speech, text, or possibly by embodied expression. Through their design, they closely emulate human conversation to communicate and interact with people. This was achieved in the artificial intelligence Turing Test. Amazon's Alexa, Google Assistant, and Siri are examples of modern chatbots that are used in everyday life.

LIBRARIES AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Technology has been a part of each and every human work. The presence of artificial intelligence technologies in all spheres of work has made the future promising. The world is becoming increasingly centered on using microelectronic-based technologies for information processing, handling, collection, retrieval, and utilization. Computer systems can now model numerous human competencies, such as word recognition, estimating, comprehending, conversing, recalling, completing shapes and figures comparison, sketching, drawing conclusions, and even active learning with the users. Scholars are building hardware and software that can simulate intelligent human features in order to boost computers' capabilities and power. Artificial intelligence has revolutionized the way libraries think and operate. Libraries in the modern age are technology absorbers from time to time. AI has found numerous applications in libraries, ranging from book filing to book delivery (Afolayan, Ogundokun, Afolabi and Adegun, 2020). The effect of artificial intelligence and its components on libraries in the near future will be enormous; the distinct differences will be different from what is currently attainable in the library. The majority of the library-oriented artificial intelligence applications developed until today or currently under development are basic business aids of the runtime. Potential applications include intelligent systems that help perform different tasks for the library, such as people, budget, collection development, scheduling, etc. These applications include systems for enhancing user services, such as ready references and information storage and retrieval as well as use (Kumar and Sheshadri 2019).

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND RANGANATHAN'S

PRINCIPLE OF LIBRARIANSHIP

The five principles of Ranganathan are fundamental to librarianship. These five principles are the hallmark of the provision of library information resources and services in the library. The following is how we see AI aligning with each of Ranganathan's five principles:

1. Books are for use

Any activity or process in the library promotes the use of library information resources. Artificial intelligent systems increase access to books or other information materials available to users and make the use of these materials easier. The majority of books are now available digitally and users get to use them more than before because they have become more accessible.

2. Every person his book

Libraries serve a wide community of users, irrespective of the type of library. Therefore, the library acquires information resources to meet a wide variety of needs. Every individual has that particular book or information material that meets their information needs at that point in time. It is important that library patrons get hold of the book. Intelligent systems such as the recommender system make this possible. It can recommend resources to acquire in the library to the collection development librarian as well as recommend to the user the best information material that meets the information needs of the user.

3. Every book its reader

Each book has its own audience. Books or other information resources should not be on the shelf and should not be used. No matter how little the population might choose to use such materials, they must have a proper place in the library. AI helps mediate between them and creates a function that not only brings users to the book but also brings the book to the users.

4. Do not waste the time of a user

This is the apex goal that the application of AI in libraries seeks to achieve. Users get busier and impatient. An intelligent system can quickly decipher the needs of a library patron and answers to their queries are provided to the user. Also, an intelligent algorithm makes it possible

to find the fastest route from the user's current location to an information resource location in the library. This smart technology can sense users' and books' locations and offer directions to connect them together.

5. Library is a growing organism

Libraries today are not what they were a decade ago. This is because a library is a dynamic institution and should never have a static outlook. Some growth occurred in the theory and practice of librarianship

The application of AI to libraries and information centers also brings growth and library patrons are better served.

LIBRARY PROCESSES AND THE APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

AI for Cataloguing Application of AI for cataloguing has focused on descriptive cataloguing because it is regarded as rule-based (AACR2). Artificial intelligence techniques can be applied through two approaches for cataloguing of information materials. First, a human-computer interface, in which the cataloging effort is split between the intermediary (human) and the support system (AI); and second, a system with full cataloguing abilities integrated with an electronic publishing system, in which text is generated digitally, it can then be passed through knowledge-based systems, and the cataloging process is done with little or no human intervention. Researchers have faced stern challenges in every endeavor to transform AACR2 into the highly structured guidelines required for coding into the system (Afolayan, et al, 2020). Digital libraries can utilize expert systems in the process of cataloguing and going through digital collections. The use of this digital library based expert system will enable patrons to go through the collection, read through the resources, and download the preferred information through the online system. The application of data mining aids the usage of intelligent library retrieval in cataloguing processes. Also, data mining can be used in online library systems to help establish users' information needs. They help library users' choice of appropriate keyword/expression in information retrieval. Several studies focus on the user-centred structure of recommender systems for library catalogs and also in other library divisions (Mogali, 2014).

AI for Circulation (OPAC)

Artificial intelligence can help with easy retrieval of library materials in the OPAC at the circulation area. NLP can assist in retrieving relevant information from catalogues, databases, indexes and help to reduce language barriers. Users can state their information requirements during the information retrieval process in their natural language, making the search and retrieval process easier and more fruitful. This enables users to state complex retrieval languages. Library users may not recognize the indistinctness of their search and retrieval strategy/method; this can be solved by the use of AI assistive technology in search tools. The usage of NLP for Dialog database searches would facilitate library users to search Dialog databases directly, with little or no assistance from information professionals. A clientele using an electronic catalog in a library may desire to have the catalog understand a particular keyword or a complete sentence. Human librarians are well trained in search & query as well as natural language, which puts them at an advantage and can act as an intermediary between the machine and the library clientele. Some URLs or web addresses are also case sensitive or have specific instructions that must be followed for perfect retrieval of the needed information resources. Library clientele need to become computer literate to take advantage of these new tools in the library (Afolayan, et al, 2020).

AI for Reference Services

Intelligent systems are developed to refer library patrons to information resources likely to answer their reference queries within the library system. More work has been done on systems for reference services than on any other service or section in the library to enable users to obtain information resources and have their reference queries answered in real-time through developed digital reference resources and services in libraries (Chemulwo and Sirorei, 2020). The aim of these systems is to guide library patrons to a suitable reference resource, especially when a librarian is not available to help them. Some reference referral systems cover a particular or restricted subject area (highly specialized domain or subject area), while some cover knowledge as a whole (general reference in its coverage). The reference service is a crucial activity of any library and the artificial intelligence tools will function as a complement to the reference librarian. The following are some of the examples of the application of artificial intelligence tools for reference services: AMSWERMEN is an agricultural knowledge-based system that answers reference queries or questions about topics in agriculture. It narrows down the subject of

the query and the type of tool needed using a series of menus. It can function as a front end to external databases or as a consultation system with CD-ROM reference tools (Mogali, 2014).

AI for Collection Development

AI tools can be utilized in selecting vendors or book dealers for library materials. An intelligent system to identify a vendor or book seller can be designed based on previously successful transactions in supplying publications of a specific kind. Such tools would be of particular importance in the procurement of information materials that are less routine, such as conference proceedings, publications in foreign languages or other countries, and certain technical reports, among others. Also, studies have revealed that AI systems have also been developed within the librarianship profession to assist in the process of selection. Such systems include: The Monograph election Advisor, which is an innovative effort in applying this emergent technology to building library information resources. Specifically, the system modeled the item-by-item decision task that a subject bibliographer carries out in selecting monographic resources. The system's knowledge base must be sufficient and the interface features must be sufficiently simple to ensure that the library can obtain the desired results from the AI system.

AI for Indexing

Indexing of library resources, especially periodicals, is another area where AI tools are being designed. The basis for document retrieval is indexing. The purpose of indexing is to enhance precision ensuring that the fraction of the retrieved material is appropriate); and recall (the percentage of appropriate materials retrieved). The keywords which have been determined by an expert (indexer) or a body as being fundamental to human thought on a specific topic will be programmed into the electronic database in away that will generate the citation on the computer screen for an article or material whenever a searcher inputs these keywords in the proper sequence into the system. Indexing a periodical article entails identifying key components, translating them into verbal descriptions, and choosing and allocating controlled vocabulary terminologies that are conceptually equal to the verbal descriptions. The purpose of automating the cognitive features of indexing is to enhance consistency and indexing quality. The indexing systems can automatically select the proper favorite terms to allocate the

appropriate subdivisions based on the information provided by the indexer (Afolayan, et al, 2020).

BENEFITS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE APPLICATION IN LIBRARIES

In order to benefit from the application of AI in libraries, library staff need to have a shift in their view of AI. Instead of perceiving AI as a disruptive tool that would displace library professionals and traditional library practices, librarians and management can learn from how AI is perceived in other professions in which it is being applied. AI should be seen as a way to tackle problems in the actual world.

AI Improves Operational Effectiveness and Efficiency

Libraries can determine and boost the organizational effectiveness and efficiency of library services by enhancing the provision of information resources and service efficacy while decreasing operating costs through automation, digital asset management, and optimized research data governance. Collection analysis, visualization, conservation and preservation, and reducing the cost of providing library services can be achieved with the development of artificial intelligence tools in library processes and services. Implementing intelligent systems for the provision of library information resources and services can help develop innovation or creativity that further improves operational effectiveness and efficiency.

CHALLENGES OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE APPLICATION IN LIBRARIES

Artificial Intelligence is still hampered by several technological, social and economic issues. Despite librarians and library administrators' increased recognition of the importance of integrating new technologies, there are still significant internal reservations prohibiting artificial intelligence techniques from entering the information management sector. These challenges include but are not limited to the following:

Financial Uncertainty

Globally, whenever public funds and revenue dwindle and socio-economic or political changes are happening, cultural organizations and institutions such as libraries frequently suffer reductions in their allocations. Libraries can neither show value for financing nor demonstrate

cost-effective practices, especially not without incorporating technological advancements to improve their physical facilities, introduce innovative services, as well as enhance the user experience for library users. All these require additional funding. The absence of appropriate information and knowledge concerning the operational benefits and effective cost-savings of the application of artificial intelligence techniques can offer to libraries makes it challenging for libraries and library personnel to establish the value of incorporating these emerging technologies into library systems. Thus, today's libraries often swim in financial constraints and are unable to show value without major funding investment. Also, the majority of AI systems are proprietary software. Research into AI-based innovations is not yet a popular trend in libraries, and broader debate and clarification among experts is still required.

Openness to Change

Throughout the world, most librarians are scared that AI will take over the work environment and render them jobless. Humans are notoriously resistant to change in operational processes and the introduction of advanced technologies. Staff in libraries frequently exhibit obstinance, even defensiveness, when it comes to technological transition. This might be due to a variety of beliefs, technophobia, or even fear of losing their jobs.

Technical Knowhow and Slow Learning Curves among Library Staff

More and more libraries are expressing interest in implementing highly innovative processes and technological applications. However, the majorities of libraries do not understand or know how the tools function and the adoption rates remain stiff among library personnel. The use of AI tools and technologies is being hampered by skill gaps in digital literacy skills. Users' Privacy When fed huge amounts of data; artificial intelligence eventually begins to recognize specific data sets through machine learning. Personal information has become a product that can be abused for nefarious activities. Data privacy, which has always been a valuable asset to libraries, may be jeopardized by AI, which is even more so in today's technological environment. Librarians must protect users' privacy by allowing them to communicate with AI systems in an anonymous manner. Also, because inquiries and search queries are recorded, this information can be used against individuals. Requesting and obtaining essays from Artificial Intelligence systems poses a risk, as private information may be gathered through machine learning.

Linguistic Capabilities Chatbots possess limited memory, and their processing capacity does not support a large vocabulary or the ability to handle a variety of conversational styles. Developers must predict the forms of interaction and build appropriate replies to them, which is a tough challenge for any multilingual nation because dialects vary by region, and programmed interactional styles may not be appropriate for all types of conversations.

Understanding of Users' Emotions

Human creativity and empathy would be played down because of AI's efficiency, resulting in a future wherein the library's connectedness to its community and valuable human attributes would be undermined and scarce. Human beings are superior to machines because they have emotions and can feel each other's emotions. Empathy is a key characteristic of any library staff; it makes the provision of information resources and services better and leads to satisfaction of the users' information needs. AI should not be allowed to take values away on the basis of information access and exchange of that information, but should be engaged to do things, to aid and process functions differently.

Other challenges encountered include bias, which occurs when algorithms are designed to function based on developer bias, or commercial organizations, which can lead to disparities in librarianship. As a result, the transparency and accountability of artificial intelligence systems are being called into question. Also, the quality level or intelligence of a given artificial intelligence system is defined by two key aspects: logical algorithms, which are technical in nature, and corpus capacity, which is data-related. With technical developments occurring at such a rapid speed, more and more complex algorithms are being developed and optimized. To keep up, an increasing number of crawlers would be needed to acquire the internet and enhance its intelligence.

CONCLUSION

The application of Artificial Intelligence is a developing technology in the field of librarianship. Artificial Intelligence has promising potential for ease and improved provision, processing, use, as well as security of information materials in the library. Researchers in LIS should collaborate with experts in AI to solve teaching and research problems related to the application of AI in libraries. This will open up opportunities in librarianship and the provision

of information resources and services to library patrons will be effective and efficient. Despite artificial intelligence being applied in various aspects of the library, most of its applications are still in the theoretical stage, which is more or less limited and cannot be really implemented. This is due to the fact that library AI hardware equipment and research investment is insufficient, big data collection and data mining are facing difficulties, library artificial intelligence talent teams are in short supply, and artificial intelligence thinking in the library business is lacking, especially in the Global South countries like Nigeria. Librarians should not be afraid of these intelligent systems taking over their jobs, but should be ready to improve their knowledge to be able to engage these systems and improve their productivity.

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